

Association and Hydration of Silver Nitrate in Acetonitrile at 25°C

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Hydration constants can be obtained from the association constant K_A determined by electrical conductivity measurements of silver nitrate in acetonitrile containing small amounts of water. The system silver nitrate-acetonitrile-water, whose characteristics are known from several investigations, offers the possibility of determining the hydration constants of the nitrate ion alone, since here, because of the predominant heteroselective solvation of silver nitrate in the binary solvent system, the hydration of silver ion is negligibly small. In the concentration region for water studied (water content up to 2M) the association constant K_A diminished much faster than expected on the basis of the changes in dielectric constant. This decrease can be understood as due to the hydration of the nitrate ion by one water molecule. Since the hydration of the ion pair can also be neglected, there exists a competition between the hydration and the ion pair formation of the nitrate ions. This hydration constant is found to be $1.7M^{-1}$.

SEVERAL experiments¹ of the system silver nitrate-acetonitrile-water have shown that the silver ions are preferentially solvated by acetonitrile molecules, whereas the nitrate ions are preferentially hydrated. This heteroselective behaviour is so characteristic that it is present throughout the composition range of the solvent mixture. Among other factors, the equilibrium constant for association of ions with solvent molecules is an important measure of solvation effects. Thus, Koeppe *et al*² determined the association of acetonitrile with silver ions in aqueous solutions by potentiometric titration. For the determination of equilibrium constants for weaker interactions such as that of water with the nitrate ion, other methods must be employed. Chantooni and Kolthoff³ measured the saturation concentrations of slightly soluble electrolytes in acetonitrile containing water and calculated the hydration constants of some univalent cations and anions. These equilibrium constants are usually of the order of magnitude of constants calculated on the model of a statistical distribution of solvent molecules in the solvation sphere of the ions. Values of the same magnitude were found for hydration constants by Cogly *et al*⁴, using the NMR method for electrolytes in propylene carbonate-water mixtures; from the chemical shifts of water, making simple non-thermodynamic assumptions, the hydration constants of single ions could be determined.

In the present work it will be shown that from the association constants determined from the electrical conductivity in the presence of water the hydration constants can be obtained. The choice of the system silver nitrate-acetonitrile-water made

it possible to obtain the hydration constant of the nitrate ion, since on the basis of earlier experiments this system revealed predominant selective solvation of silver ions by acetonitrile, and thus hydration of silver ions could safely be considered absent in the low concentration range of water studied here.

Experimental

Purification of Materials :

The main impurities in acetonitrile are acrylonitrile, from which it is commercially produced, water, and hydrolysis products such as ammonia, acetic acid, and amides^{5,6}. Several methods of purification have been developed by Coetzee⁷, O'Donnell⁸, Forcier and Olver⁹ and others. A discussion of these methods is also available¹⁰. Starting with CH_3CN puriss. (>99.5% of Fluka AG) we employed both the Coetzee method and that of Forcier and Olver. The products obtained showed a conductivity near $1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and a water content of 1×10^{-3} molar determined by Karl Fischer titration. The method proposed by Forcier and Olver gave spectroscopically purer samples. After final distillation in a 30 plate Oldershaw column, the acetonitrile was completely transparent down to 210 nm and the worst sample showed only an absorption of 10% at 200 nm. The IR and Raman spectra were identical with those presented in literature^{11,12}.

The H_2O used in our studies was thrice distilled in a quartz vessel bubbled through with N_2 ; the conductivity was less than $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

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KCl for standardisation of the cell was repeatedly recrystallised from distilled water and dried for 6 hrs at 120° in vacuum. AgNO₃ Merck p.a. 99.8% was considered sufficiently pure¹³.

Measurement of Conductivity :

The measurements were carried out in a conductivity cell carefully constructed for precision measurements after the model presented by Barthel¹⁴. The electrodes were lightly platinized¹⁵. Means of mixing the solution in the cell outside the electrodes was built into the construction. The solutions were prepared by raising the concentration of the electrolyte in a reservoir containing the solvent and fitted with a dropping cup device containing known weights of the solute⁵. The cell could be filled and emptied under pressure of solvent-saturated pure N₂. Doubly thermostated water maintained the temperature of a silicon-oil bath, constant within ±0.003° at 25°, into which the cell was kept in position. A self-made bridge and an auto-balance precision bridge (Wayne Kerr B331 MKII) were employed in the measurement of conductivity. Both had been tested for their reliability and frequency-dependence¹⁶. The cell was standardized using dilute solutions of KCl¹⁷ at intervals during the experiment. The constant of the cell was found to be 0.4321 ± 0.0002 cm⁻¹.

Results

The physical properties of the solvent mixtures used—from pure CH₃CN up to about 2M H₂O per litre—are given in Table 1. They are obtained partly by interpolating values in the literature¹⁸ close to the range of our observations. The dielectric constant D, viscosity η, and density ρ vary only little and that monotonously, thus justifying the interpolation. k' is the solvent conductivity.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF THE SOLVENT MIXTURES : WATER-ACETONITRILE

Expt. No.	H ₂ O		D	η × 100 (poise)	ρ (g/ml)	k' × 10 ⁷ (Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
	M	Mole%				
1.	0	0	36.1	0.356	0.77677	1.04
2.	0	0	36.1	0.356	0.77677	1.02
3.	0.0809	0.16	36.19	0.3562	0.77710	1.772
4.	0.0823	0.43	36.17	0.3567	0.77729	1.489
5.	0.1757	0.92	36.26	0.3573	0.77763	1.290
6.	0.2116	1.11	36.29	0.3577	0.77780	1.374
7.	0.2512	1.31	36.32	0.3580	0.77799	1.532
8.	0.2959	1.54	36.36	0.3583	0.77820	1.363
9.	0.3697	1.92	36.43	0.3589	0.77855	1.661
10.	0.3921	2.03	36.45	0.3590	0.77866	1.426
11.	1.7465	8.45	37.54	0.3686	0.78511	1.641

The conductivity was measured in the range 4 to 40 × 10⁻⁴M concentration of the electrolytes in the mixed solvents. The results are given in Table 2. It is known^{19,20} that AgNO₃ shows some association in CH₃CN (association constant K_A ≈ 75M⁻¹). Since the conductivity equations developed in the different schools (Fuoss-Onsager, Pitts, Falkenhagen *et al*) show no marked advantage of one over another^{21,22} in our concentration range and since most commonly analysis is undertaken on the basis of the Fuoss-Onsager equation, we chose the Fuoss-Onsager-Skinner equation for analysis²³. This equation can be written in the form given in(14) suitable for a flow chart analysis :

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_0 - S \sqrt{\alpha c} + E \alpha c \log (6E_1 \alpha c) + L \alpha c - A \Lambda f_{\pm}^2 \alpha c$$

The symbols have the usual meaning^{23,24}. A Fortran programme was developed on this basis and the conductivity data analysed with a Univac 1108. The aim of the analysis was to obtain reliable values of Λ₀ and A⊕. A value of a = 3.5 Å was assumed for the ion size parameter²⁰ in the input data, together with the fairly accurate values of Λ₀ and K_A obtained by the Shedlovsky approximation²⁴. Through iteration, an optimal fit for the three variables Λ₀, L(a), and A was obtained for each solvent mixture system. The values, thus obtained, are presented in Table 3. The activity coefficient f_± was calculated using the Debye-Huckel equation :

$$-\ln f_{\pm} = \frac{ke^2}{2DkT(1+ka)}$$

Discussion

From a number of studies carried out in the system AgNO₃ in CH₃CN – H₂O, namely the determination of transport numbers¹⁹, NMR studies¹, observation of phase separation temperatures²⁵, potentiometric and optical measurements^{2,26}, it is known that the silver ion is selectively solvated by acetonitrile whereas the nitrate ion is preferentially hydrated. Conductivity measurements of AgNO₃ in CH₃CN²⁰ have shown that there is some association of the salt in this solvent. It is, therefore, to be expected that, if this association in pure CH₃CN is taken on the basis of pure electrostatic association of the ions, the addition of water to this solvent would reduce the association in a manner no longer explicable by pure electrostatic attraction. The association theory of Fuoss²⁷, for example, based on the simple picture of charged sphere in dielectric continuum for ions in the solvent, will no longer be capable of accounting for the variation of the ion association merely from the variation in the dielectric constant of the various acetonitrile-water mixtures. Applied to the present system containing

* The variable A obtained in the analysis is identified with the association constant K_A²⁸.

⊕ A few cases, where analysis gave negative value for L, were not further considered because of uncertain physical significance.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF THE CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENTS

Exp. No.	1		2			3		
$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$
3.486	181.209	+0.032	8.890	172.274	+0.023	7.870	174.774	-0.082
12.310	168.283	-0.059	13.409	166.962	-0.085	11.121	170.468	+0.054
20.460	160.857	-0.168	18.518	161.760	+0.062	16.538	164.548	+0.212
24.560	156.858	+0.108	23.261	157.761	+0.009	21.499	160.457	-0.144
29.150	153.504	+0.241	28.805	153.647	-0.005	27.308	155.885	-0.055
33.750	150.834	-0.080	33.716	150.449	-0.057	34.079	151.411	-0.022
38.110	148.843	-0.079	38.471	147.554	+0.025	39.591	148.170	+0.070
$c \times 10^4$	4		5			6		
$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$
7.068	176.427	-0.036	8.035	175.079	-0.026	6.276	177.778	+0.085
12.125	170.106	+0.135	13.055	169.401	+0.013	11.103	172.303	-0.203
17.340	165.192	-0.125	18.405	164.535	-0.036	16.829	166.366	+0.145
21.542	161.599	-0.074	24.076	160.141	-0.037	23.741	161.014	-0.006
28.065	156.700	+0.088	30.201	156.047	-0.024	29.530	157.085	+0.018
33.111	153.508	+0.052	36.251	152.524	-0.029	36.243	153.143	-0.020
38.911	150.277	-0.055						
$c \times 10^4$	7		8			9		
$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$
4.535	179.054	+0.002	5.307	179.981	-0.032	5.038	179.142	+0.198
9.630	172.410	-0.038	10.557	173.462	+0.071	10.076	174.156	-0.489
16.582	165.473	+0.066	16.841	167.606	-0.055	15.967	168.497	+0.064
23.654	160.036	-0.050	23.611	162.337	-0.029	21.128	164.692	+0.069
30.648	155.425	-0.008	30.556	157.734	+0.036	26.991	161.028	-0.062
37.929	151.317	+0.009	36.529	154.349	-0.016	32.630	157.778	-0.037
$c \times 10^4$	10		11					
$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$	$c \times 10^4$	Λ	$\delta \Lambda$			
4.462	179.140	-0.028	5.324	173.878	+0.001			
8.433	174.009	+0.095	10.910	169.780	+0.020			
12.640	169.897	-0.065	16.055	166.569	-0.021			
16.461	166.544	-0.003	27.466	161.115	+0.024			
21.100	163.019	+0.022	33.248	159.014	-0.008			

c = concentration of AgNO_3 (Mol/l solution).
 Λ = equivalent conductivity ($\Omega^{-2} \text{cm}^2 \text{equiv}^{-1}$).
 $\delta \Lambda = \Lambda$ (theoretical) - Λ (experiment).
The experiments are numbered as in Table 1.

TABLE 3—PARAMETERS OF THE CONDUCTIVITY EQUATION OF FUOSS-ONSAGER-SKINNER

Expt. No.	Λ_0	L	A
1.	192.36	1875.4	81.74
2.	191.54	735.8	67.26
3.	192.59	955.14	68.38
4.	192.50	965.6	61.48
5.	191.85	993.2	56.50
6.	191.89	610.8	49.89
7.	190.59	834.5	51.88
8.	192.43	578.1	46.28
9.	190.08	160.5	29.32
10.	189.94	923.3	44.17
11.	184.11	2415.2	31.54

Experimental data (Table 3) which differ in $\delta \Lambda$ by less than 0.09 units (0.05%) are used in the analysis. When all data are used, e.g. in pure CH_3CN (No. 1) Λ_0 varies by 0.03, A by 1.4, and L by 130 units.

very small amounts of water, the association constant K_a depends on the anion hydration constant, since the silver ions are preferentially solvated by acetonitrile.

The variation of Λ_0 , the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution, with water content in acetonitrile is shown in Fig. 1. The value of Λ_0 in pure CH_3CN is $191.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ equiv}^{-1}$ and decreases to 184.1 units with 2M/l of water present in the solution. The initial rise in Λ_0 with the first addition of water was found also for silver picrate, picric acid and silver nitrate in acetone²⁸. Walden's product $\Lambda_0 \eta$ is constant within 0.5% almost throughout the experimental range of water content. This constant value presents an almost constant value of the ionic size on the basis of the Stokes law²⁹. This amounts to 4.8 Å for the salt. Hittorf transference numbers of AgNO_3 in CH_3CN ¹⁰ give 2.66 Å for Ag^+ and 2.17 Å for NO_3^- .

Fig. 1. The equivalent conductivities ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{equiv}^{-1}$) at infinite dilution of silver nitrate in acetonitrile containing various amounts of water.

The association constant was analysed further as it was the principal object of interest. Fig 2 shows the course of the association constant with water content in acetonitrile. AgNO_3 is practically completely dissociated in water³⁰. The K_A value in

Fig. 2. Association constant K_A of silver nitrate in acetonitrile containing various amounts of water.

acetonitrile is 74.5 at 25° and decreases to half this value when the solvent contains 0.38 M water. In Fig. 3 two curves are presented : logarithm of the association constant drawn against the reciprocal of the dielectric constant. The lower curve E shows the experimental values ; it runs linear, but deviates markedly from the theoretical curve T obtained using the Fuoss formula on the electrostatic model²⁷.

$$K_T = \frac{4\pi N_A^2}{3000} \exp\left(\frac{z^2 e^2}{aDkT}\right)$$

On the basis of change in dielectric constant, only about 7% variation (of the 50% mentioned above) of the association constant is accountable at all. In

Fig. 3. $\ln K_A$ as a function of $100/D$; E : experimental values of K_A ; T : theoretical values = K_T .

this calculation, the assumption $K_T = K_A$ in pure acetonitrile was made. The corresponding value of 1.83 Å for a , although it is too small to represent the dimensions of the associate (crystal radius of Ag^+ is 1.26 Å), was used in the calculation of the theoretical values in Fig. 3. The pure electrostatic model, therefore, fails because of the selective solvation present ; there is competition between ion association and hydration of the anion. The hydration constant could now be determined on the assumption that the silver ions are not hydrated in the presence of the nitrate ion in the range of water concentration investigated. The theory of the analysis is as follows :

From these equilibria one gets the association constant K_A of silver nitrate in aqueous acetonitrile solution related to the constant K_A^0 in pure acetonitrile :

$$K_A = K_A^0 \frac{1 + \sum K_n^0 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^n}{1 + \sum K_n^- [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^n}$$

The same relation can be obtained by the method employed by Fuoss in the case of picric acid in aqueous acetonitrile⁹. We make use of the equation in the form :

$$R = \frac{K_A^0}{K_A}$$

The variation of R with water content in acetonitrile is depicted in Fig. 4. The values of R are

Fig. 4. The ratio of association constants, $R = K_A^0 / K_A$, drawn against water content of the solvent.

directly proportional to the water concentration. It could, therefore, be concluded that the nitrate ion is hydrated by a single molecule of water in this range of water content, since the variation of R in this region can be expressed by the simple equation :

$$R = 1 + K_1^- [H_2O]$$

where K_1^- is the first hydration constant of the nitrate ion in acetonitrile.

$$K_1^- = 1.7 M^{-1}$$

This value agrees with the hydration constant $K_1^- = 2 M^{-1}$ of the nitrate ion in CH_3CN found by Chantooni and Kolthoff for salts of alkali ions from solubility measurements^{3*}.

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* Water concentrations in acetonitrile are used in these calculations. The formal hydration constant, thus obtained, can be compared with those available in the literature. An estimated³¹ water activity for these low concentrations in acetonitrile would possibly reduce the value of the hydration constant K_1^- by a factor of 5 or 6; but this could well be expected to be compensated by the activity of the hydrated species as a constituent of the hydration constant given by $K_1^- = [NO_3 \cdot H_2O] / [NO_3^-][H_2O]$.

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